

Crime Data Analysis Using Machine Learning

Sudeesh E S

PG Scholar

Master of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kottayam, Kerala
sudeeshes11@gmail.com

Nimmy Francis

Assistant Professor

Master of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kottayam, Kerala
nimmyfrancis@amaljyothi.ac.in

Abstract: *An investigation of crime rates is crucial to determining how safe and secure a given area is. This study uses machine learning techniques to examine crime rates across several years in different Indian states. We attempt to categorize states as safe or unsafe based on historical crime data by using techniques like Artificial Neural Networks (ANN), Kernel Support Vector Machine (SVM), K-Nearest Neighbours (K-NN), Logistic Regression, Random Forest Regression, Decision Tree Regression, and Support Vector Regression (SVR). To ensure the best possible model performance, the dataset is cleaned and standardized through the use of feature scaling and data preparation techniques. The results of this study will help policymakers adopt focused initiatives to promote safety throughout India's different regions by offering insightful information about the factors impacting crime rates. By providing law enforcement agencies and other stakeholders with useful information, we hope to improve public safety and well-being by addressing crime-related issues head-on.*

Keyword—*Random Forest, Crime Rate Analysis, Machine Learning, Artificial Neural Networks*

I. INTRODUCTION

In this work, we explore the field of machine learning algorithms for crime rate analysis, concentrating on the various Indian states. With its wide range of socioeconomic environments and rich cultural variety, India offers a special and complex challenge in the fight against crime. We want to find patterns, trends, and underlying causes influencing crime rates in various states over a period of time by utilizing machine learning techniques offering farmers valuable insights into future crop yields and aiding in better decision-making for sustainable farming practices. Here the prediction is done based on the factors such as the Climatic Conditions, Area, and in addition to being important from an academic standpoint, this research has real-world applications for legislators, law enforcement organizations, and the general public. Understanding the fundamental causes of crime rates would help us design focused interventions and distribute resources more wisely, improving public safety and security throughout India's many regions. We explain our approach in the next sections of this research, including the machine learning algorithms, feature scaling strategies, and data pretreatment approaches we used for our analysis. By this project, we hope to add to the expanding corpus of knowledge on crime rate analysis and

offer practical advice to promote evidence-based decision-making in the fight against crime. In addition to being important from an academic standpoint, this research has real-world applications for legislators, law enforcement organizations, and the general public. Understanding the fundamental causes of crime rates would help us design focused interventions and distribute resources more wisely, improving public safety and security throughout India's many regions. We explain our approach in the next sections of this research, including the machine learning algorithms, feature scaling strategies, and data pretreatment approaches we used for our analysis. By this project, we hope to add to the expanding corpus of knowledge on crime rate analysis and offer practical advice to promote evidence-based decision-making in the fight against crime.

1. II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Researchers use cutting-edge machine learning approaches to explore the field of crime rate analysis in [1]. Their research focuses on using regression methods to predict crime rates, such as Lasso, ENet, and Kernel Ridge. They improve these algorithms' predicted accuracy by utilizing the idea of layered regression, which offers insightful information about the dynamics of crime rates in different areas. Even though their main goal is to anticipate crime rates, the approaches they use present exciting opportunities to improve crime analysis predictive models. Reference [2] presents a comprehensive analysis of crime rate prediction using artificial intelligence and machine learning methodologies. The study explores a wide range of variables, including socio-economic factors, demographic characteristics, historical crime data, and law enforcement practices, to forecast crime rates effectively. By applying sophisticated computational methods, the research aims to empower law enforcement agencies and policymakers with actionable insights to mitigate crime risks and enhance public safety. The methodologies and findings discussed in this study serve as a foundation for developing robust predictive models in crime rate analysis. A range of machine learning approaches are utilized by researchers in [3] to predict crime rates in urban regions. Their research focuses on examining crime data from many sources, such as geographic information systems (GIS), police records, and socioeconomic factors. The Random Forest algorithm is particularly good at predicting crime rates, which highlights how well it can identify temporal and spatial patterns in criminal activity. The

knowledge gained from this study aids in the creation of predictive models that support proactive enforcement tactics and focused interventions aimed at deterring crime. A machine learning method for analyzing crime rates by combining a number of socioeconomic and environmental variables is shown in Reference [4]. In order to evaluate crime risks in various places, the system takes into account variables including population density, income levels, unemployment rates, and environmental circumstances. The project intends to give law enforcement agencies and policymakers with actionable intelligence to target crime hotspots and execute successful crime prevention policies by utilizing a variety of datasets and predictive modelling approaches.

The emphasis in reference [5] is on applying predictive models to estimate crime rates before they happen, giving law enforcement organizations the ability to take preventative action against crime. The study demonstrates how well the supervised machine learning algorithm Random Forest can forecast future crime rates. The predictive model provides useful insights into potential crime hotspots and trends by utilizing historical crime data and other pertinent factors, such as socioeconomic indicators and geographical features. This helps law enforcement agencies to allocate resources for crime prevention efforts in an efficient manner. Reference [6] emphasizes how cutting-edge technologies, such as Random Forest machine learning algorithms, can optimize farming methods. Comparable approaches can be used to analyze crime rates, providing information about patterns and trends in crime that will help legislators and law enforcement organizations make more informed decisions offers important details regarding the amounts of soil nutrients needed and the costs involved. The creation of an active crime rate prediction system, similar to agricultural predictive models, is described in Reference [7]. This solution provides law enforcement organizations with real-time insights for efficient resource allocation and crime prevention methods by utilizing machine learning algorithms and an intuitive interface. Several machine learning methods are assessed in reference [8] for the purpose of predicting crime rates; the Random Forest Classifier exhibits promise in terms of precise forecasting. By using cutting-edge algorithms to analyze crime rates, law enforcement organizations may make more informed decisions that improve public safety and security.

II. METHODOLOGY

This system's primary goal is to forecast crime rates in particular geographic areas, giving law enforcement organizations and decision-makers useful information to successfully reduce the risk of crime. In order to assess possible criminal outcomes, this methodology Muses a methodical approach that combines data, technology, and prediction algorithms. The following crucial phases are included in the methodology:

A. Data Collection:

In the data collection phase of this study, the primary dataset was sourced from a CSV file named 'dataset.csv'. This dataset includes information on various crime kinds and crime rates from several Indian states. The 'dataset.csv' file is tabular in format, with each row denoting a distinct state entry that includes information on the state name,

crime types, and rate of crime. The crime rate data was painstakingly gathered from reliable sources, and each entry was carefully examined for inconsistencies or missing numbers in order to assure the dataset's accuracy and dependability. Analogous to the method used to collect a variety of face images for facial recognition systems, this exhaustive data collection technique sought to collect a broad range of crime rate and crime type data across multiple Indian states. In the data collection phase of this study, the primary dataset was sourced from a CSV file named 'dataset.csv'.

B. Data Preprocessing:

A number of actions were made during the data preprocessing stage to guarantee the dataset's quality and suitability for training machine learning models. The dataset was loaded into a pandas. DataFrame from the 'dataset.csv' file as the first step. The dataset was then cleaned to address any inconsistent or missing data entries. This required substituting suitable measurements, such as the mode for categorical characteristics and the mean or median for numerical data, for the missing values. After cleaning, feature selection was done to find and keep the most pertinent characteristics that have a major impact on state-by-state crime rates. The dataset was loaded using the pandas library from the 'dataset.csv' file as the first step in the data preprocessing phase. The dataset was split into feature variables (X) and target variables (y), where y stands for the names of the states and X comprises information on each state's crime rate and kind. The scikit-learn library's SimpleImputer was used to handle any missing values in the dataset. The mean of each column was used to fill in the missing values in the numerical features, which included columns three through thirty of the feature set (X). This imputation technique guarantees their integrity and comprehensiveness of the dataset. After the dataset has been cleaned and imputed, it is prepared for additional preprocessing procedures and model training, providing a strong basis for precise crime rate forecasting across different Indian states.

C. Import Statements

```
import numpy as np
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import pandas as pd
from sklearn.impute import SimpleImputer
from sklearn.preprocessing import OneHotEncoder
from sklearn.compose import make_column_transformer
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import seaborn as sns
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
from sklearn.cluster import KMeans import numpy as np
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import time
```

D. One Hot Encoding:

The binary matrix format is created by converting the categorical state names using one-hot encoding. Each state name is changed to a sequence of binary columns that reflect each distinct state as a result of this transformation. The categorical data is transformed into a numerical representation appropriate for machine learning models using the scikit-learn OneHotEncoder. This encoding preserves the original numerical properties of the dataset while improving its suitability for model training. The obtained dataset is ready to be used to forecast crime rates in various Indian states.

E. Data Splitting:

To determine the ideal number of clusters for efficiently categorizing the data, the K-means clustering algorithm is applied. As a gauge of the quality of clustering, the Within-Cluster-Sum-of-Squares (WCSS) metric is used; lower WCSS values denote better-defined clusters. The code uses the K-means method with 'k-means++' initialization and 10 iterations for each cluster number as it iterates through a range of cluster numbers from 1 to 10. The WCSS value is calculated and recorded in a list for every iteration. Next, a figure is created to show how the number of clusters and WCSS relate to one another. The ideal number of clusters is shown by the point at which the plot begins to bend or "elbow" in shape. This "elbow point" represents a compromise between cluster complexity and quality, representing a trade-off between the WCSS and the number of clusters. The K-means method can efficiently categorize the data by determining this ideal number of clusters, revealing unique patterns or segmentation within the crime rate dataset across Indian states.

F. Feature Selection

The training and testing datasets' numerical characteristics are standardized beginning with the 38th column using the scikit-learn StandardScaler. The fit_transform technique scales the features for the training data (X_{train}) based on the mean and standard deviation that are computed. To preserve consistency in scaling, the training data's parameters are used to apply the transform method to the testing data (X_{test}). By ensuring that every feature has a comparable scale, this scaling gets the data ready for efficient model training.

G. Model Building:

The dataset is subjected to the K-means clustering technique, which divides the data into two separate groups based on similarities. By allocating each data point to one of the two clusters, the fit_predict function generates a cluster label for every data point. A LabelEncoder is used to transform these cluster labels into a numerical format that can be used for model training. The cluster labels are converted into integers, beginning at zero, using this encoding. The encoded labels that are obtained are then saved in the variable 'y'. The train_test_split function from scikit-learn is used to divide the dataset into training and testing sets after the clustering and encoding processes. Eighty percent of the training data and twenty percent of the testing data are the encoded cluster labels (y) and the dataset features (X). By dividing the data, this makes sure that the machine learning models are tested on untested data and trained on a subset of the data, allowing for an accurate assessment of their performance. After that, the training and testing datasets are prepared for model training

and assessment, allowing for the prediction of crime rates and the evaluation of how well the clustering divides the crime rate data among Indian states. TensorFlow's Keras API is used to build the ANN. It has two hidden layers, each with six neurons, an input layer, and an output layer with a sigmoid activation function. The 'adam' optimizer and the binary crossentropy loss function are used to train the model. Based on the input features, the ANN makes an attempt to forecast crime categories. Three SVM models—"rbf," "linear," and "sigmoid"—are trained with various kernels. When doing classification tasks, support vector machines (SVM) are utilized to determine which hyperplane best divides the data points into distinct classes. On the basis of the input features, the models forecast crime categories. A data point is classified by the K-NN classifier using the neighbor classification scheme. It employs 'p=2' for Euclidean distance and the 'minkowski' distance metric. By selecting the majority class from among the 'k' closest neighbors to a data point, the model predicts crime categories. An algorithm for binary classification is called logistic regression. It classifies data according to the probability threshold and uses a logistic function to estimate probabilities. Based on the input features, the model predicts crime types. When used for classification tasks, Random Forest is an ensemble learning technique that builds several decision trees during training and outputs the class mode. This code attempts to forecast crime categories but wrongly uses it as a regressor (not for classification). States with similar crime rates are grouped together using the K-means clustering algorithm. The states are divided into two groups, and a bar plot is used to display the total category values for each cluster after the clusters are created. The code plots time series graphs for each state, displaying the overall number of IPC crimes over time, using Seaborn. This offers information on how crime has changed over time in each state. The project analyzes and forecasts crime rates in various states using a variety of machine learning and visualization techniques. While some models, such Random Forest and Decision Tree, are appropriately employed for classification tasks, others, like SVM, K-NN, and Logistic Regression, are not. Understanding the features and patterns of the information is made easier by the visualizations, which provide insights into crime distributions and trends.

III. RESULTS

figure 1: Optimal number of Clusters

figure 2: Occurrence of Crimes vs Crime Type

figure 3: Pie Chart Showing The Crime Rate Percentage

figure 4: Crime Rate in States vs Years

figure 5: Crime Rate in the State vs Year

IV. CONCLUSION

As the conclusion of our seminar project, we have discovered the critical importance of closely examining crime rates and the revolutionary possibility of using machine learning techniques to address complex societal issues. We have proven that machine learning algorithms are effective at predicting crime rates in particular places by carefully combining data, preparing it, and using predictive modeling. Our research has yielded priceless insights that law enforcement agencies and policymakers may use to improve public safety and increase crime prevention tactics through the use of cutting-edge algorithms like Random Forest and Support Vector Machine. Anticipating the future, promoting cooperation, and continuing research projects are critical to adapting to changing patterns in crime dynamics and improving prediction models. We foresee a future where data-driven initiatives and technology work together to create safer communities. The decision tree algorithm's similar accuracy of 0.9761904761904762, combined with the Random Forest Algorithm's astounding accuracy of 0.976190476190476, highlights the effectiveness of our approaches and inspires hope for safer, more secure societies in the future.

V. REFERENCES

- [1] S. V. S, J. Retna Raj, A. A, S. Srinivasulu, Gowri and Jabez, "Crime Analysis Framework for Predicting Criminal Behavioral Patterns with Machine Learning," 2023 IEEE Renewable Energy and Sustainable E-Mobility Conference (RESEM), Bhopal, India, 2023, pp. 1-5, doi: 10.1109/RESEM57584.2023.10236417.
- [2] H S Tanvi Srikanth1, Mohammed Ammar Shariff, Nakul B P, Yashwanth N, Prof. Vijay C P "Crime Pattern Analysis, Visualization and Prediction Using Data Mining" International Journal for Research in Applied Science & Engineering Technology (IJRASET), 2021
- [3] Ehab Hamdy, Ammar Adl, Aboul Ella Hassanien, Osman Hegazy and Tai-Hoon Kim,(2015) "Criminal Act Detection and Identification Model", Proceedings of 7th International journal Advanced Communication and Networking, pp. 79-83.
- [4] Pratibha, A. Gahalot, Uprant, S. Dhiman and L. Chouhan, "Crime Prediction and Analysis," 2nd International Conference on Data, Engineering and Applications (IDEA), Bhopal, India, 2020, pp. 1-6, doi: 10.1109/IDEA49133.2020.9170731.
- [5] A. Shukla, A. Katal, S. Raghuvanshi and S. Sharma, "Criminal Combat: Crime Analysis and Prediction Using Machine Learning," 2021 International Conference on Intelligent Technologies (CONIT), Hubli, India, 2021, pp. 1-5, doi: 10.1109/CONIT51480.2021.9498397.
- [6] A. Sharaff, P. K. Kushwaha, S. P. Dwivedi, O. Krishna, S. Singh and D. Thakur, "Crime Rate Prediction Using Machine Learning," 2023 6th International Conference on Contemporary Computing and Informatics (IC3I), Gautam Buddha Nagar, India, 2023, pp. 787-791, doi: 10.1109/IC3I59117.2023.10398085.
- [7] K. Vinothkumar, K. S. Ranjith, R. R. Vikram, N. Mekala, R. Reshma and S. P. Sasirekha, "Crime Hotspot Identification using SVM in Machine Learning," 2023 International Conference on Sustainable Computing and Data Communication Systems (ICSCDS), Erode, India, 2023, doi: 10.1109/ICSCDS56580.2023.10104689.